

BLEPHERIN. PART I

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The glucoside 'blepherin', obtained from the seeds of *Blepharis edulis*, Pers. (N.O. Acanthaceae), has been assigned the formula $C_{17}H_{20}O_{10}, 2H_2O$. Based on chemical studies of the hydrolytic fission products and the I. R. and U. V. data, it is tentatively proposed that blepherin is 3:4-dihydro-5- β -D-glucosyloxy-9-hydroxy-(α)-dihydrofuran-*isocoumarin* (II or III: R = H; R₁ = glucosyl). It seems to be the first dihydrofuran-dihydroisocoumarin to be detected in nature.

Blepherin, a colorless crystalline bitter principle, was first isolated by Lal (this *Journ* 1, 1936, 13, 109; 1940, 17, 269) from the seeds of *Blepharis edulis*, Pers., to which he assigned the formula $C_{16}H_{20}O_{10}, 1.5 H_2O$, m.p. 220°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 121^{\circ}.5$. He reported the preparation of its penta-acetyl, pentacarbethoxy and penta-*p*-nitrobenzoyl derivatives. Although on hydrolysis with dilute hydrochloric acid he claimed to have isolated a crystalline aglycone, m.p. 178°, neither its analytical results nor the experimental details of hydrolysis were recorded. Besides, he inferred that blepherin was a β -glucoside as it had been hydrolysed by emulsin; but he made no investigation of the hydrolytic fission products nor did he undertake the characterisation of the sugar moiety.

The first approach aimed at repetition of Lal's method of isolation, followed by hydrolysis of blepherin and structural investigation of the hydrolytic fission products. As the tedious method of isolation followed by Lal gave a very poor yield, a simpler process has been developed to obtain blepherin in fairly good quantities (0.7% of the seeds); its m.p. by repeated crystallisations could be raised to 225-26°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} = +121^{\circ}.3$. Contrary to the claims made by Lal (*loc. cit.*), molecular weight determinations of its derivatives by Rast's camphor method (M.W. of blepherin itself could not be determined by this method as it was insoluble in camphor) as well as the analyses of blepherin and its derivatives indicate the empirical formula of blepherin as $C_{17}H_{20}O_{10}, 2H_2O$. The acetylation of blepherin has, however, been achieved under two different milder experimental conditions and the m.p. of the acetate in each case was found to be 158-59° (Lal records m.p. 183°). The same product was invariably obtained even when the acetylation was done under the rather drastic condition, adopted by Lal. Moreover, the analytical results of the crystalline acetate, based on the formula now assigned to blepherin, showed the presence of five hydroxyl groups.

Contrary to the claim by Lal, the author failed to isolate the aglycone by repeated attempts to hydrolyse blepherin, under varying conditions. The neutralised aqueous solution, however, readily reduced hot Fehling's solution and Tollen's reagent; indicating the presence of a reducing sugar in the solution, since blepherin itself

has no such reducing properties at all. Failure to isolate the aglucone by acid hydrolysis may be attributed to some deep-seated change in the molecule in acidic medium, although the glycosidic nature of blepherin is clearly demonstrated. Final confirmation of its β -glucosidic character came from the fact that hydrolysis of blepherin by emulsin could satisfactorily be effected, the aglucone, $C_{11}H_{10}O_8$, being slowly deposited from the solution as yellow needles on standing, and on rigorous purification it was obtained as colorless needles, m.p. 207° (Lal records m.p. 178°). From the carbohydrate remaining in the aqueous solution, phenyl-D-glucosazone was isolated and characterised, showing that only D-glucose was formed during the hydrolysis. The hydrolysis of blepherin may therefore be represented as :

For the sake of convenience, it is proposed to name the aglucone $C_{11}H_{10}O_8$ as 'blepherigenin'.

Although blepherigenin does not give any colour reaction with ferric chloride, that it is a dihydric phenolic compound is confirmed from its following behaviours: (a) it readily dissolves in cold aqueous caustic alkalies from which it is reprecipitated by carbon dioxide; (b) it yields a diacetate and a dibenzoate by Schotten-Baumann method of acylation; (c) it forms a neutral dimethyl ether with alkaline dimethyl sulphate or methyl iodide-potassium carbonate, and (d) it rapidly reduces hot Fehling's solution and Tollen's reagent (polyhydric phenols). As blepherigenin fails to respond to the fluorescence test, it is not possibly a *meta*-dihydroxyphenolic compound with the free *para* position. On the other hand, the two phenolic groups appear to be in *ortho* or in *para* positions, as its alkaline solution rapidly undergoes oxidation in air. Thus, when pure blepherigenin, which is colorless, is dissolved in aqueous caustic soda, the solution immediately becomes yellow; on keeping at room temperature it turns deep brown and overnight it becomes dark coloured, and a humus-like material with metallic shine gradually separates. Besides, on oxidation with ferric chloride or with alkaline ferricyanide it readily gives rise to similar intractable products. Although for want of sufficient material it has not been possible so far to confirm the precise orientation of the two phenolic groups, preliminary experimental evidences, however, favour the *para* positions. Thus, failure on the part of blepherigenin to respond to the usual distinctive tests of an *ortho*-dihydroxyphenol, such as colour reaction with ferric chloride or ammonium molybdate and precipitation with basic lead acetate, is not inconsistent with the view that blepherigenin, in all probability, is a *para*-dihydroxyphenolic compound.

Examination of the infra-red spectrum of blepherigenin dimethyl ether reveals the presence of a conjugated δ -lactone. A comparison of its carbonyl stretching frequency with those of mellin methyl ether (3:4-dihydroxy-8-methoxy-3-methylisocoumarin; Blair and Newbold, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 2872) and of 7-methoxyphthalide (Duncanson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 75, 1331), both in solution

and in the solid state, given below, strongly suggests the existence of a dihydroisocoumarin ring in blepherigenin dimethyl ether.

Blepherigenin dimethyl ether	...	1708 cm ⁻¹ (solid)	...	1720 cm ⁻¹ (CHCl ₃)
Mellin methyl ether	...	1710 (solid)	...	1741 (CCl ₄)
7-Methoxyphthalide	...	1748 (solid)	...	1782 (CCl ₄)

This conclusion is in keeping with the view that the carbonyl frequencies in the cases of lactones, lactams and cyclic ketones increase as the size of the ring diminishes. (Rusmussen and Brattain, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1949, 71, 1073).

Furthermore, Blair and Newbold (*loc. cit.*) have observed that in the ultra-violet region the strong bathochromic shift of the maxima in dihydroisocoumarins, compared with those in the phthalides, is so noteworthy that it might be of diagnostic use in deciding between the isomeric dihydroisocoumarin and phthalide structures. Thus, when the ultraviolet absorption spectrum of blepherigenin is compared with those of mellin and the phthalides (Blair and Newbold, *loc. cit.*), the bathochromic shift of the maxima in blepherigenin is found pronounced, and therefore it strongly supports the presence of a dihydroisocoumarin ring.

	λ_{max}	ϵ
Blepherigenin	2500 Å	13,437 - 4
Mellin	2460	6,500
7-Hydroxyphthalide	2320	8,700
7-Hydroxy-3-methylphthalide	2320	7,500
7-Hydroxy-3-ethylphthalide	2340	7,000

Conclusions from the chemical studies are also in conformity with the foregoing inference. Although the neutral dimethyl ether of blepherigenin is insoluble in aqueous caustic potash (40%), the presence of a lactone ring is deduced by its behaviour towards boiling alcoholic alkalis. The sodium or potassium salt of the lactone, which was eventually isolated as a solid, readily dissolved in water and the aqueous solution, on acidification, immediately deposited the original dimethyl ether. Since the lactone ring is very stable, all attempts to prepare its derivatives (e.g., hydrazide formation, methanolysis with sodium methoxide, esterification with dimethyl sulphate or dizomethane) have so far not met with success; but reduction with lithium-aluminium hydride to the corresponding diol has, however, been successfully effected, and the presence of the lactone ring thus substantiated.

In blepherigenin (C₁₁H₁₀O₃), the functional groups containing all the oxygen atoms have been accounted for as follows: Out of the five oxygen atoms, two are accounted for in the phenolic hydroxyl groups; two in the lactone ring of the dihydroisocoumarin, and the remaining one, in the absence of any alkoxy (Zeissel) or ketonic (the dimethyl ether failed to react with Brady's reagent, hydroxylamine, semicarbazide; no characteristic absorption in the I.R.) or alcoholic group (the dimethyl ether did not react with acetic anhydride, 3:5-dinitrobenzoyl chloride; no characteristic absorption in the I.R.), presumably must be present in ether

linkage. Moreover, blepherigenin does not contain any allylenic double bond because its dimethyl ether does not give the usual tests for unsaturation, nor can it be catalytically hydrogenated. Besides, it fails to respond also to Legal's test for $\beta\gamma$ -unsaturated lactone. The Kühn-Roth oxidation of the aglucone with chromic acid fails to give acetic acid, and therefore absence of *C*-methyl in blepherigenin is indicated.

Some deductions may now be made as to the nature of the nuclei. Blepherigenin, as best representing the facts so far known, is a *para*-dihydroxy-dihydroisocoumarin compound, and therefore the partial structure (I) may be assigned to it. Since it is optically inactive, substitution at 3:4-positions is eliminated; the absence of *C*-methyl is also indicated by the negative Kühn-Roth determination. In view of the fact that one oxygen atom is present in ether linkage and that there is no unsaturation in the molecule, the moiety C_5H_8O must represent a single saturated ring, and the only possible way to accommodate this moiety is in the form of a dihydrofurano ring. This gives rise to two possibilities, and the structure of blepherigenin may thus be provisionally represented as (II) or (III).

Although confirmatory evidence is at present lacking, certain experimental observations suggest the existence of the dihydrofurano ring. Traces of a phenolic acid, obtained by caustic potash fusion of blepherigenin dimethyl ether (II or III: $R=R_1=Me$), gave intense port-wine colour with alcoholic ferric chloride, thereby indicating the creation of a new phenolic group, presumably caused by the fission of the postulated furano ring. Moreover, zinc dust distillation of blepherigenin yielded minute quantities of a sublimate which also gave a port-wine colour with ferric chloride (blepherigenin itself does not give colour with ferric chloride)—evidently again due to a new phenolic group formed by the rupture of the furano ring. The quantities of the phenolic products, in both the cases, were too meagre to permit isolation and characterisation. However, the final choice between the structures (II) and (III) will be the subject of the next communication.

The orientation of the glucose residue in blepherin has been determined as follows. Evidence bearing on the chelated condition of one phenolic group in blepherigenin and, hence, its proximity to the carbonyl group of the lactone (incidentally established the presence of a conjugated lactone) was found in the

failure of one of the two phenolic hydroxyls to react with diazomethane. Thus, while blepherigenin with diazomethane yielded the monomethyl ether (A) (II or III: R=H; R₁=Me), m.p. 163°, blepherin, on prolonged methylation with MeI-K₂CO₃ and subsequent hydrolysis of the glucosyloxy group by emulsion, gave blepherigenin monomethyl ether (B), m.p. 154°. An admixture of the two isomeric monomethyl ethers, (A) and (B), melted at 132-42° with previous sintering at 127°. This establishes that the monomethyl ether (B) is different from its isomer (A), and must therefore have the structure (II or III: R=Me; R₁=H). Consequently it follows that the structure of blepherin may be (II or III: R=H; R₁=glucosyl). The two monomethyl ethers, (A) and (B), on further methylation with MeI-K₂CO₃, as expected, furnished the same dimethyl ether (II or III: R=R₁=Me), obtained directly from blepherigenin by the action of methyl iodide and potassium carbonate.

During recent years, quite a number of natural products having the isocoumarin or dihydroisocoumarin structures have been reported, but the existence of a hitherto-unreported dihydrofuranodihydroisocoumarin is noteworthy and creates interest. For final confirmation of the proposed structure of blepherin, further investigation, both by degradative and synthetic methods, is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL*

Isolation of Blepherin (II or III: R=H; R₁=glucosyl).—The seeds of *Blepharis edulis*, Pers. (5 kg., batches of 200 g.) were finely powdered and refluxed with acetone (800 c.c. for 200 g.) for 2 hours and the extract was filtered. The extraction was repeated with fresh acetone thrice altogether. The combined extract was freed of acetone as completely as possible by distillation and the residue was set aside for a week; when a thick crystalline mass with dark oily impurities separated. It was then refluxed with ethyl acetate (250 c.c.) for 2 hours and after keeping overnight, the crystalline solid was filtered off. The dark brown crystals, thus obtained, were again boiled with ethyl acetate (100 c.c.) for 1 hour, left for 6 hours, and then filtered. The brown solid was collected and dissolved in the minimum quantity of hot water; on keeping, the aqueous solution solidified to a thick paste of needles. Three to four crystallisations from the minimum quantities of hot water removed most of the colouring matter from the crystals. Three further crystallisations from boiling alcohol, followed by two crystallisations from hot water, yielded the colorless crystals (18 g.) free from allantoin with which it was contaminated.

Concentration of the combined aqueous and alcoholic mother-liquors gave further quantities of blepherin, largely contaminated with allantoin. Allantoin was removed as follows: Impure blepherin was dissolved in the minimum quantity of boiling water and the hot solution was seeded with pure blepherin when immediately crystalline needles separated, multiplying to a thick paste. The vessel was then kept in a bath of cold water for five minutes and immediately filtered, even

* All m.p.s are uncorrected. Micro-analyses were done by Drs. Weiler & Strauss, Oxford, and by Dr. Gore, Dept. of Chemical Technology, Bombay Univ.

though the solution was warm. Two to three such operations usually purified the blepherin and made it free of allantoin (N test negative). Again the mother-liquors were worked up thus to recover blepherin (19 g.); total yield 35 g. of blepherin from 5 kg. seeds (0.7%). A very pure specimen, obtained by repeated crystallisations from ethyl alcohol had m.p. 225-26°; $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 121.3$ (c, 0.03135 g. in water). (Found: C, 48.98, 48.97, 48.70; H, 5.57, 5.97, 5.60. Calc. for $C_{17}H_{20}O_{10}$, $2H_2O$: C, 48.57; H, 5.71%). [Found (in a specimen dried in a vacuum at 150° to const. wt.): C, 52.06; H, 5.38; loss of H_2O , 6.51, 6.11. Calc for $C_{17}H_{20}O_{10}$, $0.5H_2O$: C, 51.9; H, 5.34; loss of H_2O , 6.4%].

Blepherin crystallises from water in long colorless needles; on keeping for a few days in contact with water, these needles changed to beautiful rectangular plates. It is soluble in hot ethyl and methyl alcohols, insoluble in ethyl acetate, benzene, chloroform, acetone and petroleum ether. It readily dissolves in aqueous alkalis from which it is reprecipitated on acidification with mineral acids. It is difficultly soluble in cold HCl (conc.); the colorless solution on boiling becomes intense yellow. It is insoluble in cold H_2SO_4 (conc.); on warming, the solution becomes pink and finally is charred when heated. The aqueous or alcoholic solution of blepherin does not give any colour reaction with ferric chloride; it does not respond to Legal's test, nor does it reduce Fehling's solution. It has no unsaturation ($KMnO_4$ and Br_2 in CCl_4 not decolorised) and has no alkoxy group (Zeisel negative).

Blepherin Penta-acetate (II or III: $R=CH_3CO$; R_1 =tetra-aceto-glucosyl)

(a). Blepherin (0.2 g.) (dried for 5 hours in vacuum at 120°), dissolved in warm pyridine (1 c.c.), was mixed with acetic anhydride (2 c.c.) and allowed to stand at the room temperature for 24 hours. The solid acetate, isolated in the usual way, was crystallised from the minimum quantity of methyl alcohol; a few further recrystallisations from dilute methyl alcohol furnished blepherin penta-acetate as colorless felted needles, m.p. 158-59° (slow heating), with previous sintering (prolonged) at 122°. [Found: C, 51.95, 52.11; H, 5.42, 5.35; M.W. (Rast), 598, 600. $C_{17}H_{16}O_{10}(CH_3CO)_5$, $1.5H_2O$ requires C, 52.17; H, 5.31%; M.W., 621].

(b). A mixture of dried blepherin (0.1 g.), acetic anhydride (3 c.c.), fused sodium acetate (0.5 g.) was heated for 2 hours on a water-bath and worked up in the usual way. Two crystallisations from dilute methyl alcohol yielded the *acetate* as felted needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. 158-59°, with previous sintering at 122°.

(c). Repetition of Lal's method (*loc. cit.*, 1940) gave the same *acetate*, m.p. and mixed m.p. 158-59°, sintering at 122°.

Blepherigenin (II or III: $R=R_1=H$): *Acid Hydrolysis*.—Blepherin (1.0 g.) was refluxed with dilute H_2SO_4 (50 c.c., 2%) for 5 hours, when the initially colorless solution became red; on keeping, the solution gradually became darker and no solid was deposited. Ether extract of the acid solution gave only traces of the unchanged starting material. The reaction mixture was then carefully neutralised with $BaCO_3$ and filtered; the neutral red filtrate, on keeping, deposited slowly a dark brown, humus-like solid during the course of a week, which could not be crystallised. The aqueous solution, however, readily reduced hot Fehling's solution.

The same result was obtained when the hydrolysis was carried out with methanolic aq.HCl (8%). The solution after refluxing became dark red from which a deep brown intractable material was obtained.

Hydrolysis with oxalic acid solution (5%) gave a similar dark-coloured solid which failed to crystallise.

Hydrolysis with Emulsin.—Blepherin (2 g., 10 batches), dissolved in water (75 c.c.) at room temperature, was treated with a little emulsin and allowed to stand at a warm place (30-32° preferably) with the mouths of the flasks plugged in with cotton. After 3-4 days, the initially colorless solution became yellow and traces of a yellow solid material started separating; a little emulsin was further added at this stage and set aside. During the course of a fortnight from the start of the experiment, fairly appreciable quantities of solid (in some flasks the solid had yellow colour and in some, red) were deposited from the yellow supernatant liquid and, as traces of fungus were noticed, it was worked up without further delay. The yellow/red precipitate was filtered off from the aqueous solution (P), dissolved in warm methyl alcohol and filtered from insoluble impurities; the clear methanolic solution, on concentration on a water-bath, almost solidified to a paste of tiny yellow needles. A few crystallisations from boiling water yielded blepherigenin as yellow needles, m.p. 205°. Further quantities of blepherigenin were recovered from the aqueous solution (P). Concentration on a water-bath under reduced pressure gave a thick paste of yellow/red needles of blepherigenin, contaminated with the unchanged blepherin. Repeated crystallisations from hot water (the solubility of blepherin in hot water is much greater than that of blepherigenin) finally furnished the aglucone as pale yellow needles, m.p. 205°. Working up in this way a total of 6.5 g. of blepherigenin was collected.

A specimen of blepherigenin was purified by dissolving in aqueous NaOH, precipitating it by CO₂ and then crystallising repeatedly from a mixture of dioxan-petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and finally from dioxan, when colorless prismatic needles, m.p. 207°, were obtained; λ_{max} 2500 Å (ϵ 13434), 2800 Å (ϵ 7513); λ_{min} 2290 Å (ϵ 6509), 2720 Å (ϵ 6378). [Found: C, 58.4, 58.8, 58.53; H, 5.0, 4.5, 4.35; M.W. (Rast) 205, 220. C₁₁H₁₀O₅ requires C, 59.4; H, 5.0%; M.W., 222).

Blepherigenin sublimes under vacuum at 120° to colorless needles, m.p. 207°. Purification by this method was found wasteful as charring occurred on continued heating.

Another method to obtain colorless needles was to dissolve the red/yellow needles of blepherigenin in boiling water and to add a drop of HCl (conc.), followed by a small amount of zinc dust. On quickly filtering the hot colorless solution, colorless needles separated out on cooling which were soon filtered off as otherwise, on keeping in solution the crystals became coloured again. This procedure was, however, found to be also wasteful.

The red/yellow crystals of blepherigenin, when dissolved in the minimum quantity of dilute aq.alkalies and acidified with dilute HCl, a thick paste of pale yellow needles was obtained. On repeating this process thrice, the colour gradually

became much paler, but another repetition furnished the aglucone as intensely coloured as the original specimen.

Properties of the Aglucone, Blepherigenin.—It readily dissolves in cold aqueous alkalis, imparting a yellow colour to the solution; dilute mineral acids, even CO_2 , reprecipitate the original compound. The alkaline solution overnight becomes dark brownish red and after a few days a deep brown amorphous solid with metallic shine separates out. It is insoluble in cold aq. Na_2CO_3 and aq. NaHCO_3 . Oxidation with FeCl_3 or alkaline ferricyanide gives a dark brown precipitate. It does not give colour with aqueous alcoholic FeCl_3 nor does it respond to Legal's test. It readily reduces hot Fehling's solution and Tollen's reagent. It fails to give the fluorescence test or colour with ammonium molybdate. No precipitate is obtained with basic lead acetate solution. Its alkaline solution gives a brown precipitate with benzene diazonium chloride solution. Oxidation with chromic acid (Kühn-Roth) to determine the C-methyl failed to give acetic acid. It is not soluble in cold H_2SO_4 (conc.), but on warming it dissolves with a wine-red colour. It is insoluble in cold HCl (conc.), but on boiling it dissolves, imparting a yellow colour to the solution.

Characterisation of the Sugar Moiety.—The aqueous solution, left after the isolation of blepherigenin and unchanged blepherin in the foregoing hydrolysis experiment, was concentrated under reduced pressure to a thick syrup, taken up in a little water and filtered from the insoluble residue. A test portion of the aqueous solution immediately reduced Fehling's solution. Aqueous phenylhydrazine acetate (0.4 c.c. of a mixture containing phenylhydrazine 10 c.c., acetic acid 10 c.c., diluted to 25 c.c. with water) was added and after 5 minutes at 100° , a precipitate formed (required for the formation of D-glucosazone, 4-5 minutes). One hour later, the mixture was cooled, the osazone collected and purified by crystallisation from dilute alcohol. Its crystalline form was identical with that of a specimen similarly prepared from D-glucose and after recrystallisation from dilute alcohol it had m.p. and mixed m.p., $204\text{--}205^\circ$ (with rapid heating). (Found: C, 60.6; H, 6.2; N, 15.4. Calc. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{N}_4$: C, 60.3; H, 6.4; N, 15.6%).

Blepherigenin Diacetate (II or III: $\text{R}=\text{R}_1=\text{CH}_3\text{CO}$).—A solution of blepherigenin (0.2 g.) in NaOH (5 c.c., 2N) was mixed with acetic anhydride (5 drops) and a little crushed ice. On vigorous shaking, immediately a solid separated out which on recrystallisations from dilute methyl alcohol yielded the pure *diacetate*, m.p. 177° , with previous sintering at 173° . [Found: C, 57.4; H, 4.4. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{O}_6(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2$, 0.5 H_2O requires C, 57.2; H, 4.9%]. [Found in a specimen dried in vacuum at 110° : C, 58.3; H, 4.6. $\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_9\text{O}_6(\text{CH}_3\text{CO})_2$ requires C, 58.8; H, 4.9%].

A solution of blepherigenin in pyridine was treated with acetic anhydride, allowed to stand for 24 hours and worked up in the usual way, when the *acetate* was obtained, m.p. and mixed m.p. 177° .

Blepherigenin Dibenzoylate (II or III: $\text{R}=\text{R}_1=\text{PhCO}$).—Blepherigenin (0.2 g.), dissolved in NaOH (10 c.c., 2N), was treated with benzoyl chloride (4 drops) and shaken until a solid separated out. Several recrystallisations from methyl alcohol gave colorless needles, which on further crystallisation from ethyl acetate furnished

the *dibenzoate* in rectangular prisms, m.p. 207°. [Found: C, 66.6, 67.04; H, 4.05, 4.14. $C_{11}H_8O_3(C_6H_5CO)_2 \cdot H_2O$ requires C, 66.9; H, 4.4%]. [Found in a specimen dried over P_2O_5 in a vacuum desiccator: C, 68.3; H, 4.5. $C_{11}H_8O_3(C_6H_5CO)_2 \cdot 0.5H_2O$ requires C, 68.3; H, 4.3%].

Blepherigenin Dimethyl Ether (II or III: $R=R_1=CH_3$).—To ensure success it is essential that blepherigenin should be as little coloured as possible, otherwise the yield of the dimethyl ether is considerably lowered. Different samples (red and yellow) of blepherigenin (10 g.) were taken together and dissolved in the minimum quantity of cold NaOH solution (2N) when a dark solution was obtained. A current of CO_2 , washed through water, was passed until the solution became saturated and the phenolic compound completely separated out. The crystals of blepherigenin were again similarly treated and finally crystallised from boiling water (charcoal), when very pure pale yellow needles (9.55 g.), m.p. 207°, were obtained. These were thoroughly dried in an oven at 110°.

(a). The purified dry blepherigenin (3 g.), dissolved in anhydrous pure acetone (100 c.c.), was refluxed with methyl iodide (10 c.c.) and anhydrous K_2CO_3 (8 g.) for 10 hours. The inorganic salts were filtered off from the solution and washed with portions of warm acetone. The filtered solution was then evaporated, and the residue washed with dilute NaOH, followed by water, and dried in a desiccator (5.5 g. of the dimethyl ether obtained from 9 g. of blepherigenin). Vacuum distillation (1 mm/bath temp., 180-85°) of the methyl ether gave colorless distillate which soon solidified to colorless needles. One crystallisation from dilute methyl alcohol (ice-chest) yielded the pure *blepherigenin dimethyl ether* as silky needles, m.p. 71° (5 g. from 5.5 g. of the crude dimethyl ether). [Found: C, 62.2, 62.3; H, 5.8, 6.0; OMe, 24.8; M.W. (Rast), 235. $C_{11}H_8O_3(OMe)_2$ requires C, 62.4; H, 5.6; OMe, 24.8%; M.W., 250].

Unlike blepherigenin, it does not reduce Fehling's solution or Tollen's reagent; it is insoluble in aq. alkalis. It does not decolorise aq. $KMnO_4$, Br_2 in CCl_4 and does not absorb hydrogen on Pd-C catalyst in methyl alcohol at room temperature. On refluxing with Ac_2O -NaAc the unchanged material is obtained. It does not form 2:4-dinitrophenylhydrazone, oxime and 3:5-dinitrobenzoate. It fails to give colour test with gallic acid and H_2SO_4 (conc.) for methylenedioxy group. With H_2SO_4 (conc.) in cold it gives no colour, but on warming a violet colour is produced. It is insoluble in cold HCl (conc.) and unlike blepherigenin, on boiling it neither dissolves nor imparts any colour.

(b). To a solution of blepherigenin (0.5 g.) in aq. NaOH (5 c.c., 2N) dimethyl sulphate (4 c.c.) was added in portions alternated with aq. NaOH (25 c.c., 2N) to keep the solution alkaline all the time. It was warmed occasionally to maintain the temperature at 40-60° and the mixture shaken during the operation. After 3 hours a dark oil separated which was extracted with ether, and the extract washed with water. The ethereal solution after drying over Na_2SO_4 , on evaporation, left a red oily residue which on keeping or on seeding deposited the *blepherigenin dimethyl ether* in clusters of prismatic needles. A few crystallisations from dilute methyl

alcohol (ice-chest) afforded the pure methylated product, m.p. and mixed m.p. 70°. The yield by this method was much lower than the MeI-K₂CO₃ method.

Blepherigenin Monomethyl Ether (A) (II or III: R=H; R₁=CH₃).—Blepherigenin (1 g.), dissolved in methyl alcohol (30 c.c.), was treated with an ethereal solution of diazomethane (from 5 g. of nitrosomethylurea) and left overnight. The brownish solution next day was refluxed until the colour changed to pale yellow; the ether was evaporated off and the residual liquid taken up in a little methyl alcohol, and water was added to turbidity. After keeping it in the refrigerator for 2 days crystalline needles separated. Repeated crystallisations from dilute methyl alcohol (refrigerator), furnished the pure *monomethyl ether* as colorless needles, m.p. 163° (Found: C, 60.6; H, 4.8; OMe, 13.4. C₁₁H₈O₄.OMe requires C, 61.0; H, 5.0; OMe, 13.1%).

It dissolves in aq. NaOH and is reprecipitated on acidification. On further methylation with MeI-K₂CO₃ it yields the dimethyl ether, m.p. and mixed m.p. 71°.

Blepherigenin Monomethyl Ether (B) (II or III: R=CH₃; R₁=H).—A mixture of blepherin (2 g.), anhydrous K₂CO₃ (7 g.), MeI (7 c.c.) and pure anhydrous acetone (150 c.c.) was refluxed for 24 hours. After filtration and evaporating off the acetone, a colorless viscous oil was left which could not be crystallised. It was taken up in a little cold water in which it was soluble; the aqueous solution was treated with emulsin and set aside. After a fortnight, colorless rosettes of needles separated which were dissolved in the minimum quantity of hot methyl alcohol, water added to turbidity and left in the refrigerator; beautiful colorless needles were gradually deposited which on two crystallisations from dilute methyl alcohol (refrigerator) gave the *monomethyl ether (B)* in slender needles, m.p. 154°. [Found: C, 60.4; H, 5.3. C₁₁H₈O₄.OMe requires C, 61.0; H, 5.0%]. When mixed with the monomethyl ether (A), it melted at 130-42°, with previous sintering at 127°.

On further methylation with MeI-K₂CO₃ it yielded the dimethyl ether, m.p. and mixed m.p. 71°.

Characterisation of the Lactone Ring

(a). Blepherigenin dimethyl ether (0.2 g.), dissolved in alcoholic KOH (10 c.c., 40%), was refluxed for 2 hours and the solution after dilution with a little water was concentrated on a water-bath to a very small bulk (ca. 2-3 c.c.). The only potassium salt separating on ice-cooling solidified. It was dissolved in water and acidified with HCl (dil.), when the original starting material was precipitated. When the solution of potassium salt was cooled to 0° and acidified with minimum ice-cold acetic acid, the original dimethyl ether was obtained instead of the free acid.

(b). *Lithium-Aluminium Hydride Reduction of the Lactone Ring*.—To an ice cold suspension of LiAlH₄ (1.0 g.) in anhydrous ether (60 c.c.) blepherigenin dimethyl ether (1.0 g.) was added in portions and the mixture shaken for 2 hours at room temperature. It was then again cooled in ice, treated with water (not much excess) and left in the refrigerator overnight. The ether layer was decanted and

the residue extracted with fresh portions of ether; the combined etheral solution was washed repeatedly with water till the washings were neutral to litmus. Evaporation of the ether after drying with $MgSO_4$ gave a syrupy residue, which when rubbed with a little petrol-ether (b.p. 40-60°), afforded crystals contaminated with brown oily impurities. After decanting the petrol-ether it was repeatedly triturated with petrol-ether (or preferably with CCl_4) to remove the oily impurities and the almost colorless crystals, thus obtained, were dissolved in the minimum quantity of petrol-ether (40-60°); on standing in the refrigerator the *diol* crystallised out in colorless rosettes of needles. A few such crystallisations furnished the pure product, m.p. 84°. (Found: C, 61.8, 61.6; H, 6.2, 6.5. $C_{13}H_{14}O_2$ requires C, 61.4; H, 7.0%).

(c). *Lactone Ring-opening Experiments.*—(i). *Attempted Methanolysis.*—Blepherigenin dimethyl ether (50 mg.), dissolved in methyl alcohol (5 c.c.), was treated with NaOMe solution (2 drops, 1.0 g. Na in 25 c.c. MeOH) and left for 24 hours. On acidification with acetic acid, evaporating off of the MeOH and addition of water, the unchanged starting material separated out.

(ii). *Attempted Hydrazide Formation.*—Blepherigenin dimethyl ether (50 mg.), hydrazine hydrate (2 drops) and alcohol (10 c.c.) were refluxed for 6 hours and on working up, the unchanged material was obtained.

(iii). *Attempted Esterification with Me_2SO_4 .*—Blepherigenin dimethyl ether (0.5 g.), dimethyl sulphate (1.5 c.c.), K_2CO_3 (3 g.) and pure anhydrous acetone (50 c.c.) were refluxed for 100 hours. On working up in the usual way, yellow oily residue was left which on vacuum-distillation yielded the unchanged starting material.

Alkali Fusion of Blepherigenin Dimethyl Ether.—Blepherigenin dimethyl ether (0.5 g.) was fused with KOH (2.5 g.) in a nickel crucible at 250° for an hour. The cooled product was digested with water and the brown aqueous solution, after acidification with HCl, was extracted with ether. The extract was washed with 10% aq. $NaHCO_3$ and water, dried and on evaporation of the ether, traces of a sticky yellow product were obtained which could not be crystallised.

The bicarbonate washings were acidified with HCl, and extracted with ether; the yellow ethereal solution on evaporation afforded a brown gummy residue which could not be induced to crystallise. It was readily soluble in bicarbonate with effervescence and with alcoholic ferric chloride gave a port-wine colour. The product, presumably a phenolic acid, was too meagre to permit purification and characterisation.

Zinc dust Distillation of Blepherigenin.—An intimate mixture of blepherigenin (0.5 g.) and Zn dust (8 g.) was heated in a pyrex test tube with a cold finger at 220°; pale yellow needles which sublimed in the beginning, gradually turned to reddish oily liquid. The oily sublimate, when dissolved in petroleum ether and evaporated, deposited almost colorless needles which were insufficient for purification and identification. The sublimate in alcoholic solution gave a port-wine colour with ferric chloride and rapidly became oxidised to a dark brown amorphous material in dilute alkali.

Blepherigenin dimethyl ether, when subjected to the zinc dust distillation, sublimed off unchanged at 160-70°.

Alkaline Permanganate Oxidation.—Blepharigenin dimethyl ether (1.0 g.), suspended in water (30 c.c.) containing NaOH (2 g.), was kept boiling while aqueous permanganate (4 %) was added dropwise with stirring to a 10 minutes' end-point (ca. 228 c.c. of the KMnO_4 solution required). When worked up in the usual way, a bicarbonate-soluble acidic material was obtained. The quantity being too small, it could not be purified for characterisation.

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